

Milestone MS15

Planning Preparation of the Rolling Review of Requirements Process

MILESTONE

Milestone	MS15 Initial Meeting of WP4 for planning preparation of the RRR process
Due Date	30 June 2024
Submission Date	Day Month Year
Dissemination Level	Public
Milestone Lead	Helmholtz Center for Ocean Research Kiel (GEOMAR)
Authors	Johannes Karstensen (GEOMAR) Abed El Rahman Hassoun (GEOMAR)
Contributors	Roshin Roj (NERSC) Ronan McAdam (CMCC) Dimitra Denaxa (HCMR) Samantha Hallam (NUIM) Karin Margretha H. Larsen (HAV) Rebecca Hummels (GEOMAR) Vincent Combes (CSIC) Ana Oliveira (+ATL) Beatriz Lopez (+ATL) Fabiola Silva (+ATL) Gerard McCarthy (NUIM) Fehmi Dilmahamod (GEOMAR) Giulia Bonino (CMCC) João Paixão (+ATL) Pia Englyst (DMI) Sourav Chatterjee (NCPOR) Emmanuel Eresanya (NUIM) Veera Haapaniemi (FMI) Jay Pearlman (IEEE) Steffen Olsen (DMI)
Reviewer	Chiara Bearzotti (DMI)

Table 1: Document Information

DISCLAIMER

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1 Means of verification of this milestone	4
2 Objective	5
3 Vocabularies applicable to WP4 operations	7
Measurement	8
Variable	8
Observation	8
Uncertainty	8
Heterogeneity	8
Data quality	9
Ocean observing	9
Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) and Essential Climate Variables (ECVs)	9
Best Practices	10
Sustained observing	12
Operational oceanography	13
The Rolling Review of Requirements Methodology (RRR)	14
How does the RRR work?	16
How to apply the RRR methodology to the WP4 Application Areas - A 5-steps-process	17
Step 1: Identify a Point of Contact (PoC) for the WP4 application areas	18
Step 2: Review technology-free observing requirements for an ObsSea4Clim AA	18
Step 3: Review of the observing capabilities of existing and emerging observing systems	19
Step 4: Critical Review of the extent to which observing capabilities meet the requirements for observations	19
Step 5: Statement of Guidance based on Critical review	20
References	20

ABBREVIATIONS

Table 3: List of Abbreviations

BP	Best Practice
ECVs	Essential Climate Variables
EEZ	Exclusive Economic Zone
EOVs	Essential Ocean Variables
ESAC	Earth System Application Category
FOO	Framework for Ocean Observing
GCOS	Global Climate Observing System
GFCS	Global Framework for Climate Services
GOOS	Global Ocean Observing System
NDC	Nationally Determined Contribution
OBPS	Ocean Best Practices System
OSCAR	Observing Systems Capability Analysis and Review Tool
PoCs	Points of Contacts
RRR	Rolling Review of Requirements
SoG	Statement of Guidance
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure
VIM	International Vocabulary of Metrology
WIGOS	WMO Integrated Global Observing System
WMO	World Meteorological Organization
XBT	Expendable Bathythermographs

1 Means of verification of this milestone

To accomplish this milestone, a literature review of material related to the Essential Ocean Variables and the Rolling Review of Requirements (RRR) was conducted. In addition, a series of online and one in-person meetings were organized with partners and intergovernmental and national experts from the World Meteorological Organisation (WMO) and the Global Climate Observing System (GCOS). These meetings have been synthesised in this document to enable a synchronised operation across all the tasks of WP4 and to be ready to provide input to other relevant work packages. After the preparation of the first draft, the text of the milestone was shared with the project’s partners and discussed thoroughly in an online meeting held on 5 June 2024. Major meetings that led to the production of this milestone are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Summary of all meetings that led to the content of MS15.

Meeting date	Targeted group/individuals	Main topics discussed	Type of meeting
14/02/2024	Belén Martín Míguez, WMO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RRR process at the WMO level • GCOS • Opportunities and obstacles in ocean observing and reporting 	Online
19/02/2024	Stefan Rösner, DWD, Germany	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GCOS • GCOS-Germany specifics • Obstacles at the national level 	Online
12/03/2024-14/03/2024	All partners of ObsSea4Clim	General discussion about RRR and definitions	In-person

05/06/2024	ObsSea4Clim WP4 partners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation of the draft MS15 • Agreement on vocabulary and descriptions • Integration of further comments on the document 	Online
15/07/2024	ObsSea4Clim WP4, with the presence of members from WP2 and WP3	Kick-off preparation for MS16	Online

2 Objective

An optimal global observation system enables data to serve all purposes for which the data is fit. To judge the fitness for purpose, the following requisites have to be identified:

- what the motivation for the observation is,
- which approach is chosen for the sampling,
- whether alternative approaches exist.

Depending on the chosen approach, the required spatial and temporal sampling of properties and the required accuracy of the sampled properties must be determined. By mapping the existing or planned observations against the required sampling for the design, it is possible to retrieve the information of a “sufficient for the purpose” sampling.

Besides the availability of observations in space and time, it is the uncertainty that will qualify the use of data for its use for a certain purpose and application, such as climate assessments and the provision of advice to stakeholders (e.g., fish farms) or for the characterization of marine habitats, to mention a few. **A periodic “rolling” review of observational needs, observing design and availability of fit-for-purpose data, considering temporal and spatial**

sampling, measures on heterogeneity of observations (uncertainty), and the timely availability of data go into what is summarized in the *WMO Rolling Review of Requirements* process.

Historically, the RRR process was set up and designed for applications in meteorology (e.g., weather forecasting and seasonal forecasts). The transfer of the RRR concept to oceanic applications has recently begun. Countries are interested in the RRR for ocean applications because it will allow them to optimize the use of their investment in ocean observations in the future.

However, first of all, it is of interest to evaluate how countries conduct ocean observations for climate purposes. This milestone (MS15) summarises the meetings that took place to prepare the steps to be taken for the evaluation of countries' approaches to the elements of the RRR process and the application areas (AA) chosen in ObsSea4Clim Work Package 4 (Figure 1). The ObsSea4Clim AAs do not necessarily entirely overlap with the AA defined by the WMO¹. The consortium selected the AAs of the ObsSea4Clim project. These are an opportunity to expand areas of applications so far considered in the WMO ocean application process.

¹ <https://tools.wmo.int/applicationareas>

Fig. 1: RRR and the application areas chosen in the ObsSea4Clim partnership.

An update of this milestone will be provided in May 2025 with the milestone MS16 “Meeting of WP4 (all tasks) for updating the RRR process progress” to show the progress of the WP4 tasks – and in a dialogue with other work packages.

3 Vocabularies applicable to WP4 operations

A diversity of actors operate in the space of ocean observing. Therefore, there is never common sense about the meaning of some terminologies - starting already with the meaning of “ocean observing”. In the context of this milestone, we define hereafter the vocabularies/terminologies that will be applied in our project. This vocabulary is partly aligned with the definition of the “Framework for ocean observing” (FOO; Lindstrom et al., 2012).

Measurement

A **measurement** quantifies the characteristics of an object or event, which we can compare with other things or events. Measurements are a quantitative form of recording results. This involves exact numbers, either obtained from apparatus such as volt-meters or counted frequencies.

Variable

A measurable quantity is a **variable**.

Observation

In the context of the work presented above, we also use the word **“observation”** to assess a measured variable.

Uncertainty

A reproducible estimate of the range of values within which the true value of a variable lies. Thus, uncertainty specifies **the confidence in data**. An estimate of the uncertainties is the outcome of quality control.

The metrological community has spent decades improving our understanding of measurement methods and their uncertainty. Every measurement is affected by a certain level of uncertainty. Unfortunately, the uncertainty in environmental measurements, such as ocean ones, is affected by many factors and includes quantities of influence, such as sensor drift, environmental variability within the volume being probed, etc.

An observation is impacted by many sources of uncertainty and a sensor uncertainty, provided by the sensor manufacturer for ideal lab-controlled conditions, is not sufficient to use as uncertainty.

Heterogeneity

A measure of the range of how representative a value for a system characterisation is.

Data quality

Data quality refers to the availability of “accuracy” and “precision” information, as referred to in international conventions (UNESCO, 2013).

This allows the calculation of a statistically robust uncertainty respecting confidence intervals for each measured data point, spanning the range within which the best-estimated value lies with a specified (e.g., 95%) probability. Only when this statistical information for each data point is available can the “quality” of this data point be quantitatively assessed. This implies that a data point without information about its uncertainty is neither good nor bad, but is in a kind of premature raw data state that is not yet suitable for scientific use and publication without further refinement and can not make it into an EOVS (see definition below).

Ocean observing

All activities related to the ocean observing value chain according to FOO (Lindstrom et al., 2012). These include the observational design, the definition of observing requirements, the observation, the process of data integration, and the creation and dissemination of ocean data and model products, among others. Ocean observing should NOT be mixed up with the frequently used term ocean “observation” which is, as defined above (and in (Lindstrom et al., 2012), solely the acquisition of measurable quantities in the ocean environment. All outlined in (Lindstrom et al., 2012).

Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) and Essential Climate Variables (ECVs)

Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs)² were tailored by the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS³), while the Essential Climate Variables (ECV)⁴ were

² [Essential Ocean Variables – Global Ocean Observing System \(gooscean.org\)](https://gooscean.org)

³ [Global Ocean Observing System – GOOS is a permanent global system for observations, modeling, and analysis of marine and ocean data. \(gooscean.org\)](https://gooscean.org)

⁴ [GCOS | WMO](https://www.wmo.int/gcos/)

conceptualized by the WMO's GCOS⁵. ECVs are a much older concept than EOVs.

EOVs are combined quantities and contain a value that is derived from measured variables (x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots) and at the same time a measure for the heterogeneity of the respective value ($\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3$) aka $EOV = f(x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots) \circ f(\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3)$.

EOVs and ECVs are used synonymously in the context of the operations of ObsSea4Clim WP4 and unless it matters. Consequently, a similar linkage is true for $ECV = f(x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots) \circ f(\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3)$.

A sole measured variable without a measure for its heterogeneity is not an EOv, but a measured variable (see above for definition). For example, measured oxygen is not equal to the EOv "Oxygen" because the EOv "Oxygen" should carry an uncertainty estimate. This definition may sound counterintuitive, but has good reasons. This concept also aligns with the "sustained observing" definition for an EOv as provided in FOO (Lindstrom et al., 2012). The strict link between observed quantities and uncertainties will enable the mapping of EOvs against requirements for collecting data for multipurpose applications (e.g., as reflected in OSCAR [Observing Systems Capability Analysis and Review Tool]⁶). Also, the quantification of heterogeneity/uncertainty will ensure the interoperability of data.

Best Practices

To provide **reproducible uncertainty** estimates for observational data, documentation must be provided along with the data that outlines the practices that were followed to estimate a given measure of heterogeneity.

In ObsSea4Clim we adopt the definition of the IOC-Ocean Best Practices system (OBPS⁷): "A *best practice* is a methodology that has repeatedly

⁵ [Home | GCOS \(wmo.int\)](#)

⁶ [WMO OSCAR | Observing Systems Capability Analysis and Review Tool - Home](#)

⁷ [Ocean Best Practices System](#)

produced superior results relative to other methodologies with the same objective. To be fully elevated to a best practice, a promising method will have been adopted and employed by multiple organizations"(Pearlman et al., 2019). It is, in particular, the second part, "*adopted and employed by multiple organizations*" that will be promoted and facilitated throughout the project by WP4 and other WPs. This definition calls for the synthesis of practices/methodologies created and applied by the multiple organizations involved and ultimately will enable jointly agreed-on operations releasing interoperable data. A maturity matrix to assess the maturity and sustainability of a practice was recently developed (Mantovani et al., 2024 tbc) which refines and clarifies the features of better and best practices.

The focus of ObsSea4Clim is on physical EOVs for climate. For observations to be used in climate change analysis, attributes such as long temporal coverage, interoperability, and known accuracy (often confused with "known quality") are of relevance. The latter two attributes, interoperability and accuracy are linked to Best Practices.

The optimal global observation system will enable the use of data to serve all purposes the data might be fit for – as said in the introduction, the control metric for such a system is uncertainty. The uncertainty will qualify data to be used for climate assessment, while the same data point can be also used for other important applications, such as monitoring fish farming, wind farms' siting and planning, biodiversity conservation and protection, etc. Explicitly, we do aim to minimize the acquisition of observational data that is ONLY used for one type of application, such as climate, because acquiring data is very expensive.

Best Practices should make use of standards whenever possible. However, BPs are documentation that is intended to be updated whenever needed for potential improvements (e.g., new technologies, adding other approaches), and from that perspective, BPs are fundamentally different from standards.

Standards

The International Standards Organization (ISO⁸) defines **standards** as “documents of requirements, specifications, guidelines or characteristics that can be used consistently to ensure that materials, products, processes and services are fit for their purpose” (see Nair et al., 2023). In many cases, standards are created through a “top-down” process to create a process that should be mandatorily followed. Its application can be surveyed by a legislative instrument, such as the European INSPIRE Directive⁹ that aims to create a European Union Spatial Data Infrastructure (SDI) to enable the sharing of environmental spatial information among public sector organizations, facilitate public access to spatial information across Europe, and assist in policy-making across boundaries.

At a national (and international) level, standards follow a framework embedded in metrology and aim to accurately describe the process from a measurement result and an accompanying reference. In marine sciences, standards, in a metrology sense, face various problems (see Feistel et al., 2016; Pawlowicz et al., 2016).

Sustained observing

Purposeful observational efforts in the ocean address specific observing requirements - whether for science or other monitoring applications. To provide the information that addresses requirements, a chain of operations must be executed to ultimately lead to the release of information tailored to the specifics of any requirements. The chain of operations can be “translated” into an observing design which defines the minimal criteria for time, space, and parameter sampling to capture the information (data) needed to address the requirement. The one key aspect that makes observing “sustained” is the identification of users who need data and products in a sustained way (Adams et al., 2000; Nowlin et al., 2001). For GOOS, the characteristics for sustained observations have been defined as follows (Nowlin et al., 2001):

⁸ [ISO - International Organization for Standardization](#)

⁹ INSPIRE principles: [Overview - European Commission \(europa.eu\)](#)

- Long-term measurements, once begun, should continue into the foreseeable future and as long as requirements ask for it. Continuity is sought in the observed quantity, but not necessarily in the measurement method;
- Systematic and relevant to the observing system; in other words, measurements should be made rationally, with spatial and temporal sampling, precision, accuracy, and care in calibration tuned to address the products needed by multiple users;
- The regular review of the measurement techniques to keep up with the development of new technologies and thus ensure efficiency related to science, monitoring, and costs. Trade-offs must be subjected to scientific evaluation continuously to take advantage of new knowledge and technology. The consequences might be that different observational approaches or platforms are getting more efficient via technological progress.

Operational oceanography

EuroGOOS¹⁰, the European component of GOOS, defined the term “operational oceanography” as being “*an activity of routinely making, disseminating, and interpreting measurements of the seas and oceans and atmosphere so as to: provide continuous forecasts of the future condition of the sea for as far ahead as possible, provide the most usefully accurate description of the present state of the sea including living resources, assemble climatic long term data set which will provide data for description of past states, and time-series showing trends and changes*” (Woods et al., 1997).

¹⁰ [Home - EuroGOOS](#)

The Rolling Review of Requirements

Methodology (RRR)

The Rolling Review of Requirements (RRR) is a systematic approach to continually assess and update the specifications and criteria for a project, programme or methodology. Rather than establishing fixed requirements at the outset, which may become outdated or irrelevant as circumstances change, the RRR method allows for ongoing adjustments based on new information, technological advancements, or shifts in priorities. This concept embodies principles of flexibility, adaptability, and responsiveness to change, which are crucial in dynamic fields such as meteorology and oceanography.

The WMO introduced the RRR to oversee information on evolving requirements for observations in WMO application areas¹¹. Very recently the WMO application areas also include ocean applications that go far beyond the past metocean application areas and that included surface ocean observations relevant to weather services.

To put a framework around all observations (not only metrology), the WMO introduced its WMO Integrated Global Observing System (WIGOS)¹². The WIGOS provides the regulatory framework, guidance and tools, for the weather, water, climate and other environmental observing systems managed by WMO Members and partner Organizations to be implemented, to evolve and to **contribute to fit-for-purpose observational data to all WMO applications**.

For weather forecast and related applications, the RRR is an integral, ongoing process endorsed by the WMO to systematically align the evolving needs for meteorological, climatological, and hydrological observations with the capabilities of existing and future observing systems on a global and regional

¹¹ [The Rolling Review of Requirements process \(legacy version\) | World Meteorological Organization \(wmo.int\)](#)

¹² <https://community.wmo.int/en/activity-areas/WIGOS>

scale. This process is vital for ensuring that observational data adequately supports public safety, socio-economic well-being, and environmental sustainability.

In May 2023, WMO updated the RRR process, as outlined in the Manual on the WMO Integrated Global Observing System (WMO-No. 1160, sections 2.2.4 and Appendix 2.3). This revision further underscores the RRR's crucial role in the strategic development and evolution of WIGOS, ensuring it remains aligned with the ambitious Vision for WIGOS in 2040. The RRR process is pivotal in compiling and analyzing observational requirements across WMO application areas, evaluating observing system capabilities, and assessing cost-effectiveness to identify and prioritize actions needed to address gaps between current capabilities and future needs. This comprehensive and technology-free (without regard to the technological means of observation) approach, facilitated through the WMO's Requirements database which is part of the OSCAR, underscores a commitment to a systematic, transparent methodology that draws upon expert insights and impact studies for guiding the global observing system's future direction.

The importance of RRR in ocean observations lies in its ability to enhance the effectiveness and utility of observational data for all purposes (e.g., research, monitoring, marine resource management). The Earth System Application Categories (ESACs) of the WMO RRR's framework facilitate a coordinated approach to identifying similar observational needs across diverse fields related to weather, climate, water, and environmental events. This categorization enhances the process of gathering and analyzing user requirements and also aids in crafting tailored Statements of Guidance (SoGs). These SoGs are crucial for highlighting critical gaps in observing capabilities and offering actionable recommendations to bridge these gaps, thereby ensuring that the WIGOS evolves in a manner that is responsive to the emerging needs of the global community and grounded in technological and economic feasibility.

How does the RRR methodology work?

The RRR methodology is structured around several key stages, starting with a comprehensive review of user requirements that are articulated without regard to the technological means of observation (“technology-free”). This is followed by an evaluation of the observing capabilities of current and planned systems, a critical review to determine the extent to which these capabilities meet the user requirements and the issuance of Statements of Guidance. These SoGs provide gap analyses and recommendations to address discrepancies between needs and capabilities, facilitating informed decision-making and strategic planning for future observing systems.

A distinctive feature of the RRR process is its iterative nature, ensuring that it remains a living activity that evolves in line with changes in observational requirements and technological advancements in observing systems. It encompasses a wide range of application areas, each represented by an identified point of contact (PoC) that plays a crucial role in gathering input and facilitating feedback from the global community of stakeholders. This engagement helps to ensure that the RRR process accurately reflects the collective needs and priorities of the WMO Members and associated organisations.

Moreover, this iterative process allows for integrating new sensor technologies, data processing methods, and modelling techniques as they become available, enhancing the accuracy and reliability of ocean observations (Roemmich and Gilson, 2009). For example, the [Argo program](#), a global array of autonomous floats that measure temperature and salinity profiles in the ocean (Roemmich et al., 2022), exemplifies the principles of the rolling review approach.

The argument for Argo came from the requirements of monitoring the heat content in the global subtropical and tropical oceans. Requirements included truly “global commons” linked to the improvement of operational forecast (e.g., ENSO) or the oceanic uptake of the excess heat from global warming. The six criteria that matter for any observing requirement are: horizontal resolution,

vertical resolution, observing cycle, timeliness, uncertainty and stability (where appropriate) of an observational network that monitors the global ocean accordingly were quantified in a seminal paper by White (1995). These requirements can be further differentiated to define if sufficient sampling is achieved or not.

Mapping the technology used at the beginning of 1990, which were mainly Expendable Bathythermographs (XBT) launched from merchant ships, immediately revealed that the observational efforts were not sufficient for the purpose. There was a lack of spatial and temporal coverage and likewise in accuracy (regarding the depth determination of the XBTs which is based on empirically determined fall rates). In an iterative process, the feasibility of a network of profiling floats was developed and executed. The float became a global coordination under the Argo (A real-time geostrophic array) program which has continually evolved to incorporate advances in sensor technology, data transmission, and quality control algorithms. However, under an RRR umbrella, new opportunities would arise for the requirement (e.g., global heat content). This is because many more observational platforms, other than Argo, record the temperature profiles and provide respective uncertainties that hold the quality defined by the observation design process.

The **ideal requirement** indicates that further improvements are not necessary. The **minimum requirement** indicates that data is useful but not sufficient at all levels (e.g., sampling, coverage, etc.). In between is the **breakthrough** which is an intermediate level between threshold (minimum) and goal (ideal) which, if achieved, would result in a significant improvement for the targeted application.

How to apply the RRR methodology to the WP4 Application Areas - A 5-steps-process

For each WP4 application area (AA), a similar workflow will be adopted to enable a coherent synthesis of the outputs of the WP4 tasks. The workflow also will ensure that all elements of the RRR methodology are considered in the assessments. It will strengthen an individual country's position in climate

observing if the country's perspectives and motivation are explicitly added to the assessments.

Step 1: Identification of the Points of Contact (PoC) for the AAs

Following the WMO RRR approach, each AA (task) identifies a PoC at the country level (e.g., only the countries represented in each respective task). These PoCs act as points of contact for the groups of experts working in the specific AA in their countries. As a rule, the PoC is the country's representative in a task, unless they decide differently.

The ObsSea4Clim task leader will act as across-countries PoC for the respective AA and will:

- provide synthesized inputs to other ObsSea4Clim work packages and specifically to WP2 (global systems), WP3 (indicator) and the WP4 task leaders;
- communicate inputs from other WPs to the task members;

All task members are requested to establish a dialogue with their national representatives and introduce the specific AA to the respective country's national focal points of GOOS and GCOS.

Step 2: Review of the technology-free observing requirements for each AA

Two questions need to be addressed in this step: why observing and what to observe.

Why observing? In this stage, task members assess the interest of their respective countries in observing the AA of the respective task. All motivations are important to know. Motivations could span from marine heat waves' monitoring for fish farms' protection to providing the observational database for the Nationally Determined Contributions¹³ (NDCs) report of a country, or for reporting actions to address countries' commitment to the GCOS Implementation plan.

¹³ [Nationally Determined Contributions \(NDCs\) | UNFCCC](#)

What to observe? In this stage, the task members per country will assess at a country level what user/stakeholder “products” are needed, and how often they are needed. Ideally, they differentiate here between purely national interests that rely on observing the exclusive economic zone (EEZ) of the respective country and observing that is linked to a “global common” such as the change in global heat content, and the global temperature rise. Maybe also noting that national EEZ is a contribution to the “global commons”.

For some AAs, different scientific approaches can be chosen, e.g., for quantifying the impact of mesoscale features (e.g., fronts, eddies) for the assessment of biological productivity - one may derive that from satellite data combined with empirically determined primary productivity relations or by observing vertical profiles of chlorophyll- α from fluorescence which requires to estimate what the representative space-time grid over a domain of interest is, considering the uncertainty that the user/stakeholder finds acceptable.

Step 3: Review of the observing capabilities of existing and emerging observing systems

This step again is executed at a country level by the task members. This step will outline the status quo of the observations and the mechanisms for data integration and for data products’ dissemination (with the support of WP6) to address the requirements identified in Step 2. Some visionary thinking is recommended in this step for addressing the “emerging observing systems”.

Step 4: Critical review of the extent to which observing capabilities meet the observations’ requirements

In this step, the results from Step 2 and Step 3 are merged by the task members in a review of the AA at a country level. This review will also include an exchange across all countries represented in a task and will be organized by the task lead.

Step 5: Statement of guidance based on the critical review

This last step summarizes the results of Step 4, again on a country level but across all WP4 tasks and with the involvement of WP2 and WP3. Dedicated meetings (online) are the possible venue for the synthesis. Non-ObsSea4Clim actors will be involved in the assessment which will lead to the release of statements of guidance. Attention shall be paid to all means for improved observing, exploring new investment areas, the need for new/modified data products, and alternative ways of disseminating results.

References

Adams, R., Brown, M., Colgan, C., Flemming, N., Kite-Powell, H., McCarl, B., Mjelde, J., Solow, A., Teisberg, T. and Weiher, R., 2000. The economics of sustained ocean observations: benefits and rationale for public funding, a joint publication of the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration and the Office of Naval Research, Washington, DC

Feistel, R., Wielgosz, R., Bell, S.A., Camões, M.F., Cooper, J.R., Dexter, P., Dickson, A.G., Fiscaro, P., Harvey, A.H., Heinonen, M. and Hellmuth, O., 2015. Metrological challenges for measurements of key climatological observables: oceanic salinity and pH, and atmospheric humidity. Part 1: overview. *Metrologia*, 53(1), p.R1. doi: 10.1088/0026-1394/53/1/r1

Hermes, J., 2020. GOOS Best Practice Endorsement Process. Version 1, 7pp. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.25607/OBP-926>

Lindstrom E., Gunn J., Fischer A., McCurdy A., Glover L., Alverson K., et al., 2012. "A framework for ocean observing," in *By the task team for an integrated framework for sustained ocean observing* (Paris: UNESCO). <https://repository.oceanbestpractices.org/handle/11329/558>

Mantovani, C., Pearlman, J., Rubio, A., Przeslawski, R., Bushnell, M., Simpson, P., et al., An Ocean Practices Maturity Model: from Good to Best Practices, *Frontiers in Marine Science* (submitted 2024 and under review)

Nair, R., Waldmann, C., Pearlman, J.S., Nascimento, F., Karstensen, J., Ranganathan, S. and Heron, M., 2023, June. Relating Best Practices to Standardization in Ocean Science. In OCEANS 2023-Limerick (pp. 1-4). IEEE. 10.1109/OCEANS-Limerick52467.2023.10244310.

Nowlin Jr, W.D., Briscoe, M., Smith, N., McPhaden, M.J., Roemmich, D., Chapman, P. and Grassle, J.F., 2001. Evolution of a sustained ocean observing system. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, 82(7), pp.1369-1376.

Pawlowicz, R., Feistel, R., McDougall, T.J., Ridout, P., Seitz, S. and Wolf, H., 2015. Metrological challenges for measurements of key climatological observables Part 2: oceanic salinity. *Metrologia*, 53(1), p.R12. DOI 10.1088/0026-1394/53/1/R12

Pearlman, J., Bushnell, M., Coppola, L., Karstensen, J., Buttigieg, P.L., Pearlman, F., Simpson, P., Barbier, M., Muller-Karger, F.E., Munoz-Mas, C. and Pissierssens, P., 2019. Evolving and sustaining ocean best practices and standards for the next decade. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 6, p.277. doi: 10.3389/fmars.2019.00277

Roemmich, D. and Gilson, J., 2009. The 2004–2008 mean and annual cycle of temperature, salinity, and steric height in the global ocean from the Argo Program. *Progress in oceanography*, 82(2), pp.81-100. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pocean.2009.03.004>

Roemmich, D., Wilson, W.S., Gould, W.J., Owens, W.B., Le Traon, P.Y., Freeland, H.J., King, B.A., Wijffels, S., Sutton, P.J. and Zilberman, N., 2022. the Argo program. In *Partnerships in Marine Research* (pp. 53-69). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-323-90427-8.00004-6>

UNESCO, 2013. "Ocean data standards, Vol.3," in *Recommendation for a quality flag scheme for the exchange of oceanographic and marine meteorological data* (Brest France, Ifremer). s.l.

Waldmann C, Fischer P, Seitz S, Köllner M, Fischer J-G, Bergenthal M, Brix H, Weinreben S and Huber R, 2022. A methodology to uncertainty quantification of essential ocean variables. *Front. Mar. Sci.* 9:1002153. <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fmars.2022.1002153/full>

White, W. B., 1995. Design of a global observing system for gyre-scale upper temperature variability. *Progress in Oceanography*, 36., 169–217.

Woods, J.D., 1997. The EuroGOOS strategy. In Elsevier Oceanography Series (Vol. 62, pp. 19-35). Elsevier.

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0422989497800086>

